

LEARNING ENGLISH THROUGH SOCIAL NETWORKS

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Annotation. This article analyzes the English language learning functions of YouTube and other types of social networks from a scientific and practical point of view. The analysis explores the language skills that can be improved with the help of technology and offers a number of effective tips.

Keywords: SMART education, foreign language learning, YouTube, independent education, English language, Web-resource.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ЧЕРЕЗ СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ СЕТИ

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются функции изучения английского языка YouTube и других видов социальных сетей с научной и практической точки зрения. Анализ исследует языковые навыки, которые можно улучшить с помощью технологий, и предлагает ряд эффективных советов.

Ключевые слова: SMART-образование, изучение иностранного языка, YouTube, самостоятельное обучение, английский язык, Web-ресурс.

INTRODUCTION.

We know that in the century of information and technologies we live in today, the process of information exchange in all corners of the world has accelerated. Communication and information technologies contribute to radical qualitative changes in various fields of science, especially in the field of language learning. Mobile applications that we use every day are effective in learning a foreign language, especially English. Naturally, learning foreign languages through social networks is an important factor, and many studies are currently being conducted in this regard.

Analysis shows that learning English through social media is more effective than traditional English language learning, but only social media language learning differs in terms of negative consequences such as technology addiction. However, the features of the online language learning method have not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, it is important to carry out scientific practical research on the analysis and justification of the characteristics of learning English through social networks, its differences and common aspects from the traditional learning method.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. In the course of the analysis conducted that the similarities and differences between online distance learning and traditional learning of English through social networks were determined.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY.

Currently, the concept of "SMART" is one of the main goals in the development of the educational system. In this case, the main source of knowledge is electronic, educational Internet content, providing mutual exchange of ideas and knowledge between teachers and students through technological operations. SMART or Smart education is a concept that

includes comprehensive modernization of all educational processes and methods and the technologies used in these processes.

SMART education allows young people to adapt to a rapidly changing, unstable environment by providing high-level education, responding to the challenges and opportunities of the modern world. It is possible to perform the following tasks using Web resources [Tony Erben, Ruth Ban and Martha Castaneda, 2009: 81]:

- inclusion of social network materials in the lesson content;
- independent search of information by the learner within the framework of working on the project;
- development of reading skills using Internet materials of various complexity;
- improving listening comprehension skills based on audio texts on the Internet;
- enriching vocabulary with abbreviations of modern foreign languages based on online resources;
- learning a certain language culture.

Currently, there are many sites dedicated to independent learning of foreign languages. On such sites, you can find ready-made lessons of foreign language teachers, exercises, audio recordings, and a detailed description of grammatical topics that are incomprehensible to the student. As a vivid example of this, programs such as You tube, developed by computer technology specialists, can be shown. Through the platform, it is possible to learn the language in a short period of time and by directly watching the lessons presented by native English speakers. Such programs have become more popular with the rapid development of information technologies and the increase in the number of users of the Internet and social networks.

Whether it's to learn English at a basic level for travel, or to expand your knowledge, or to prepare thoroughly before taking exams, for those who want to work abroad, you can find a YouTube channel that suits your purpose and choose to view lessons through this program at a time and place that suits you. You can learn English in several different forms of education through the YouTube platform. Grammar rules are explained in the form of presentations or videos that are pre-made and uploaded to the site, allowing the learner to get acquainted with the course of the lesson. Given that listening comprehension is also of great importance, the information can be in the form of video clips created in Python, songs and English movies with subtitles. Homework for additional practice on strengthening the learned topic is definitely given in the form of exercises, on the basis of which the learner can better strengthen the learned topic. It is desirable for a learner who plans to learn English on the basis of You Tube to be in a comfortable environment and place to master the newly learned material well. Learning English online independently at home give us a chance to save our time. Below are the most effective channels for learning English:

Interesting sites:

1. The Free Dictionary - dictionary + idioms, forum, fun games. If you register and become a member, you will earn points for reading articles: <http://www.thefreedictionary.com/>
2. Real English - conversations with people on the street in real English. Topics are grouped under individual headings: <http://www.real-english.com/>
3. Learn It! - learn English independently with peers. Answer various assignments and tasks every 3 days for 3 months: <http://learnit90.ru/>

4. Learn English with songs! Translation of words, subtitles and complete tasks: <http://www.esolcourses.com/topics/learn-english-with-songs.html>

5. A good site for learning to read English: download the text, choose a word or sentence you do not understand from the library and find out the translation of the word <http://readlang.com/>

6. The ability to download pdf magazines in English every day on the VContacte social network: <https://vk.com/stopthepress>

British Council sites:

7. For children: <http://learnenglishkids.britishcouncil.org>

8. For teenagers: <http://learnenglishteens.britishcouncil.org/>

9. For adults: <http://learnenglish.britishcouncil.org/en/>

Popular sites with a common collection:

10. A good site for users who are just starting to learn English: a variety of dialogs and basic information: <http://www.rong-chang.com>

11. Grammar, Pronunciation, Reading, Listening and Interactive Dictionary: <http://easyworldofenglish.com>

12. English Daily is a useful site for daily practice: new words, homework and exercises: <http://www.english-daily.com/>

13. Fluentu is the most convenient site for video training. Clicking on a word will pause the video and add it to the dictionary. Exercises can be done after each video: <http://www.fluentu.com/>

14. Busuu is an international association; also has paid services: <http://www.busuu.com/>

15. Duolingo — short lessons using games: <http://duolingvo.com>

In the process of watching video lessons, the learner can expand his vocabulary. It accelerates the transfer of words from the passive vocabulary to the active vocabulary by constantly reviewing videos. The main positive feature of this platform is that the learner can independently choose the schedule and time of the learning system, as well as save it on the YouTube platform itself or on a computer and other device through the Save From program for offline review. This makes it possible to increase the quality of education [Bogatko Ya.N, 2012: 69]. This type of independent and interactive learning appeals to a large number of language learners, including travelers, young mothers, students, businessmen, and pregnant women who cannot afford to go to educational centers to learn English. Teaching English through this type of teaching system can become an effective, motivating and time-saving tool.

They work side-by-side with the teacher while the student watches the video lesson. After watching the video, they can leave questions and comments about the topic. In this case, the answers can be returned as comments in written form, or another additional lesson can be presented based on the questions of the learners. Of course, to achieve a good result, it is important to choose a clearly defined time for class activities. Learners who have difficulty speaking in public with good oral skills can record their videos and post them on the YouTube platform.

RESEARCH RESULTS.

According to the results of the analysis, it can be said that social networks play an important role in teaching English today. That is, it will be easier, faster and easier to learn the language online, virtually, without using traditional books and classrooms.

According to the analysis, it should be emphasized again that it is impossible to learn the language through channels and groups in all social networks. The result can be achieved only by joining channels and groups managed by reliable, convenient, strong professionals. All of them have been mentioned above.

DISCUSSION.

As you can see from the examples above, learning a whole new language, memorizing its grammatical structure and completely unfamiliar words can make new learners feel a bit bored and feel that language learning is difficult. In fact, everything can be easily learned by making it interesting and choosing according to your character. Learning a language also plays an important role in your personal development. The best applications above will definitely help you with this.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, it should be said that at present time, it is impossible to imagine the educational process without innovative pedagogical technologies. Today, many opportunities have been created for a foreign language teacher to help make lessons more interesting. Compared with the traditional method of teaching, the transition to a new method of teaching inevitably changes the role of the teacher [Aripov H, 2008: 146]. Its task is to increase the hours of independent study of students, to help them develop their personality. Such activities allow to significantly increase the student's interest in reading and to develop communication skills compared to the traditional method.

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